

The Epitomic Surrender

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A graveyard—I cannot bear
to look upon.

It feels as if a dead man's glance might pull me down.

His silent prayer, a whisper summoning me soon.

I turn away—shaken!

O God,

not You—it's the dead I fear now.

The thought of my grave...
of facing Munkar and Nakir at its dark gate,
sends shivers through my soul.

Their questions—O God!

What's going to be my fate?

O God, I seek Your refuge now.
I fear—yes, I fear not fearing You.
Grant me guidance unwavering—
pure, and a fear of You!

From my grasp,
if even a drop of Your mercy slips,
what will I become?

A failure—or a complete eclipse?

What if, on Judgment Day, I stand unworthy?
Sinful I will be, if my virtue is overtaken by pride.
Will there be any place left for my shame to hide?

What if my deeds tip heavier toward sin?
Will I be cast, headlong, into blazing flames within?
And if I fall,
what then of my soul?

O God, keep these hands from freezing in fear.
Give me strength to reach for You—
to beg You to draw me near.
Your awe, Your light—
cleansing this heart,
make it pure as a blooming rose,
blessed by Your might.

"Inna ṣalātī wa nusukī wa maḥyāya wa mamātī lillāhi rabbil-'ālamīn."
For without it awaits
the utmost ruin...